

Investigating Extrovert And Introvert Personalities In Reading Activities Students

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Abstract: There are several factors that influence reading such as socio-cultural factors, age environment, and personality. Among the many factors found in students is personality. Personality is all the traits that can affect a person's situation, especially the way of thinking, feeling and even one's behavior. In the most famous personality is about extrovert and introvert personalities. This study aims to determine whether there is an outcome between personality traits between extroverted and introverted students in reading ability in English reading activities in the second year of Junior high school. Student from MTS Bani Usman Al Buety This research is a descriptive qualitative research. The subjects of this research are students of grade 2 MTS. Researchers use questionnaire, interviews and literature study as instruments. The results of this study shows that some students perceive their personality to have an influence on the reading activities that students undergo.

INTRODUCTION

Along with the times, the topic of personality in learning is often discussed. Because changing times or changing times makes every character of the students change and it becomes a challenge for a teacher because not only follows learning that changes over time but also has to deal with the personality of students who are increasingly changing in each era. Reading is one of the basic language learning skills that students must learn. Reading can provide students with a valuable source of information that can improve their thinking to generate ideas from the written text they are reading. In addition, (Klingner et al., 2007) argued that reading is an activity to understand texts and gain information and knowledge.

(Wachyuningsih & Setyaningsih, 2010) adds that reading is understanding the written text of It is a complex activity that involves both perception and

thinking, and consists of two interrelated processes: word recognition and comprehension. Detection of word refers to the process of recognizing how the written symbol corresponds to the spoken language. Reading involves the activity of understanding the text and the information in the text. In order to understand the text and make some points from it, the reader needs to understand the text. Therefore, (Brassell, 2008) reading and understanding cannot be separated on the other hand, describe reading comprehension as the ability to acquire or use it to understand or understand information from written text. information. In other words, reading means not only reading every sentence in a paragraph, but also understanding the content of the text. In other words, the reader can identify the main idea of the paragraph, get the information from the text, complete the reading properly, and find the purpose of the text. English reading comprehension is usually closely

associated with discussions about skimming, scanning and skipping. (Henry Guntur Tarigan, 2015) Tarigan argues that reading is a process carried out and used by readers through written language in an effort to get the author's message.

In general, Extroverts are the type of people who are more concerned with what is happening around them, rather than an emotion in their own mind. Extroverts are often described as sociable, party-going, have lots of friends, and someone who needs someone to study with. In contrast to the introverted personality who prefers to be alone and lost in thought. (Wulandari et al., 2016) There are also different learning styles such as extroverted students prefer to participate and study in groups and introverts prefer to study alone.

This study analyzes two articles that will become previous research. Several studies have been conducted to determine the impact or comparison of extroverted and introverted personalities in speaking classes. By Rieke Ayu Oktriani and friend in 2021. Entitled, *A Comparative study between Extrovert and Introvert Student's Achievement in English Conversation*. The results showed that there was no significant difference in achieving the final scores of the English Conversation course on those two personalities.

Another research by Novita Paradila and friends in 2020. Entitled, *The Students' Extrovert And Introvert Personality Toward Speaking Performance*. The results reveal that dominant extrovert students had the same difficulties as: mispronouncing, showing, and having doubts. It can be said that extroverted students are quite confident in terms of eye contact and movement criteria where these things relate to the characteristics of extroverts. While on the other hand Introverted students, they get "good" and "bad" scores in the score.

Data shows that introverts dominate the same as extroverts who are about mispronouncing, muttering and having doubts.

The last Another research by Rofi'i and friends in 2018. Entitled, *A Comparative Analysis on Extrovert and Introvert Students Towards Their Speaking Skill*. The results showed that there is no different result between the extrovert and the introvert students in their speaking skill. Groups, the extrovert and the introvert students can perform better English speaking skill through their own way of learning

The previous research above has a correlation with this study, namely finding out how the effects and comparisons between extroverted and introverted personalities are on students. The researcher also uses data from articles that discuss this theme in conducting this research. Researchers use this type of material because we can learn a lot from the behavior of each individual or society. There are various ways to improve our knowledge, education, culture and science.

It can be seen that from all previous studies, none of them show their research that discusses studies outside of speaking. This research is interesting and can be useful for students and teachers because it can help gain a different understanding of the study of the four skills in English. Students and teachers will be able to find out how the influence of personality can affect the learning process or activity in reading and find out how it happens. Researchers are interested in conducting research based on the explanation given above.

THEORETICAL SUPPORT

Personality is a human method of thinking about reality. Personality is also tendencies towards reality. And in another

sense, human personality is a mindset *aqliyah* and a soul pattern *an-nafsiyah*. Personality is a social behavior consisting of mimics, feelings, specific characteristics, resilience, support, needs and assumptions of being integrated into a person when interacting with others or aimed at certain conditions.

According to modern psychology, personality is a dynamic organization of individual psychophysical systems that determine his unique adjustment to his environment. John Milton (Karim, 2020) revealed that personality is the arrangement of the elements of the mind and soul that determine the differences in the behavior or actions of each individual. The term personality also means the consistent character traits of an individual, which give him an identity as a particular individual. (Brassell, 2008) define personality as the organization of biological, psychological, and sociological factors that underlie individual behavior. These biological factors include physical conditions, character, sexuality, nervous system, the maturation process of the individual concerned and also other biological disorders. The psychological factors include elements of temperament, feelings, learning abilities, desires, skills and so on. Sociological factors that affect the personality of an individual can be in the form of a process of socialization obtained since childhood. Whether we realize it or not, every individual has a different personality type. And what is familiar is about these extrovert and introvert personalities. According by (Littauer, 2006) Extroverted personality tendency That is the tendency of a child to direct his attention out of himself so that all the attitudes and decisions he makes are based on the experiences of others. They tend to be friendly, open, active and sociable. The child with extroverted personality tendencies usually has many

friends and is liked by many people because his open and friendly attitude is different from that of an introvert, Tendency to introverted personality That is the tendency of a child to withdraw from his social environment. The attitudes and decisions he makes to do things are usually on his own feelings, thoughts and experiences. They usually like calmness, are aloof and quiet, feel uncomfortable in the crowd and do not need other people because they feel that their needs can be met by themselves.

According (Sastrawidoyo, 2021), extroverts are influenced by an objective world, outside of themselves. The orientation is focused on the mind, the basic feeling is mainly determined by the environment, both social and non-social. Extrovert is the tendency of individuals to direct their psychic energy on external objects outside themselves, in their social environment. An extrovert attitude directs a person to an objective external world, namely the world outside himself. Thoughts, feelings and actions are determined by the social and non-social environment. An extroverted attitude encourages people to have a positive attitude towards their environment. (Willoughby, 2021) defines that introverted individuals have cognitive organizational characteristics that are closed by beliefs and disbelief about reality, are organized by absolute beliefs and are dominated by a frame of mind that cannot tolerate other people. An introverted attitude directs individuals to the subjective world, their actions and thoughts are subjective. Introverts tend to have a negative self-concept because they lack self confidence and avoid communicating with other people. He was afraid that other people would mock him. In a communication situation, he will be more silent. Introverts are typically people who prefer to spend time alone or with one or two friends they feel close to.

Introverts often need time alone to recharge after being in a social environment. Usually, an introvert will draw energy from a quiet reflection of himself. However, many think that an introvert is a typical person who is shy or antisocial, even though that is not part of the nature of introverts.

Reading is one of the basic language learning skills that students must learn. Reading can provide students with a valuable source of information that can improve their thinking to generate ideas from the written text they are reading. In addition, (Klingner et al., 2007) argued that reading is an activity to understand texts and gain information and knowledge. Reading is an activity that mixes physical processes but also mentally. This mixing means that when doing reading activities it is not only physically working, but also the mind and mentally co-working in it. by (Nunan 2005) which states that a skill that will interpret and derive meaning from printed words is reading. Reading makes the reader's eyes spin and makes the reader's brain spin the ideas and knowledge that the reader has and gets. Meanwhile, reading is also an active process of the reader to understand the written language to obtain information and knowledge. It also supported by (Ahuja 2007) stated that sensory and mental process are involves reading because the use of eyes and mind in same time.

As it is stated by (Grellet 2010), reading is an active skill. Reading definitely has strategies such as checking, guessing, predicting, and asking oneself questions. Furthermore, (Sabouri 2016) said that reading will build a meaningful illustration of a literary work by using a strategy of reading Activities for reading need to have as their focus five key areas of instruction, which are:

- Phonemic awareness
- Phonics skills

- Fluency in reading
- Vocabulary building
- Text comprehension

(Wachyuningsih & Setyaningsih, 2010) adds that reading is understanding the written text of It is a complex activity that involves both perception and thinking, and consists of two interrelated processes: word recognition and comprehension. Detection of word refers to the process of recognizing how the written symbol corresponds to the spoken language. Reading involves the activity of understanding the text and the information in the text. In order to understand the text and make some points from it, the reader needs to understand the text. Therefore, (Brassell, 2008) reading and understanding cannot be separated on the other hand, describe reading comprehension as the ability to acquire or use it to understand or understand information from written text. information. In other words, reading means not only reading every sentence in a paragraph, but also understanding the content of the text. In other words, the reader can identify the main idea of the paragraph, get the information from the text, complete the reading properly, and find the purpose of the text

METHOD

The research method used in this research is Descriptive qualitative research is used as an approach to conducting this research. A qualitative approach is used to investigate a particular problem phenomenon so that it Can be understood clearly (Creswell, 1986) The participants in this study were 20 students from grade 2 Mts Bani Usman Al Buety. To collect data, researchers used online and offline media to interview several students and made a questionnaire to measure students' general abilities.

Data Collection

The data collection used is:

Interview

Interview is a process of get information for-research purposes by questioning and answering face to face between the interviewer and the respondent or the person being interviewed, with-or-without using-interview guidelines. The essence of this interview data collection technique is that in every use of this technique there are always several interviewers, respondents, interview materials, and interview guidelines. The interviewer is a person who uses the interview method as well as acts as a leader in the interview process. Respondents are interviewees, asked for information by the interviewer. Interview guide is an instrument used to guide the course of the interview.

Questionnaire

This research instrument uses a questionnaire that aims only to see how much dominance between extroverted and introverted personalities in second graders from MTS Bani Usman Al Buety. The researcher also met directly with several students and then gave some questions that will be used as data.

Data Analysis

After all data was collected from data sources in the field, then the data was analyzed descriptively qualitatively. Data analysis also aims to find useful information, conclusions and support for decision making. Data analysis is a very important research stage because through data analysis the researcher obtains the form of the research carried out

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Interview

List Question :

1. *In your opinion, does personality affect a person's interest in doing something, especially reading?*
2. *What do you usually do to have an interest in reading?*

3. *Are there external influences (environment) that make you lazy/diligent in reading?*
4. *Do you think there are psychological factors (ekstrovert and introvert) in reading activity?*

Introvert

introvert is mostly focused on the world within himself. An introvert personality is a thinker, less sociable or social, and prefers to spend time alone or in small groups. And the view in the interview process from introvert students can be seen below:

Research : In your opinion, does personality affect a person's interest in doing something, especially reading?

Students :

- AR : Very influential because introverts like calm and that they get one of them by reading
- KLB : No, because the influence of interest is caused by habits or abilities possessed.
- R : Yes I feel it has an effect

Research : What do you usually do to have an interest in reading?

Students :

- AR : I will cultivate curiosity in myself and discuss many things with my friends. Then I will get more information on the matter by reading.
- KLB : Usually I do by reading comics for starters
- R : Usually I read short and light stories.

Research : Are there external influences (environment) that make you lazy/diligent in reading?

Students :

- AR : The outside influence that makes me diligent in reading is when discussing something interesting with friends. And what makes me lazy to read is when I follow friends to play

- KLB : Yes, it could be due to family factors too
- R : yes.

Research : Do you think there are psychological factors in reading activity?

Students :

- AR : It's because if someone thinks 'reading is boring', they jump to conclusions without knowing what really happened.
- KLB : No.
- R : yes.

Extrovert

Extrovert is the tendency of individuals to direct their psychic energy on external objects outside themselves, in their social environment. An extrovert attitude directs a person to an objective external world, namely the world outside himself. Thoughts, feelings and actions are determined by the social and non-social environment. And the view in the interview process from extroverted students can be seen below:

Research : In your opinion, does personality affect a person's interest in doing something, especially reading?

Students :

- KA : In my opinion, it is very influential because most people now prefer to use cellphones so they are lazy to read.
- GA : No, because I think the influence of interest is due to the habits you have

Research : What do you usually do to have an interest in reading?

Students :

- KA : Looking for a title or material that is fun and not monotonous
- GA : Usually I do by reading my favorite novel for starters. Then followed by reading history book.

Research : Are there external influences (environment) that make you lazy/diligent in reading?

Students :

- KA :The environment is very influential on reading, especially if a lot of people play on cellphones, so they don't focus on reading
- GA : Yes it really affects me. The environment can make me a diligent or lazy child.

Research : Do you think there are psychological factors in reading activity?

Students :

- KA : There must be since there are so many cellphones, we are lazy to read and study.
- GA : Yes. Because I love changing moods every day.

Based on the results of interviews addressed to several students, most of them answered that their introverted personality played an important role in English reading activities. Introverts prefer to spend time in non-physical activities, such as reading. However, there is one teacher who said that personality does not affect interest in reading or reading activities. Because the teacher said that reading is a mandatory activity that every student must have. In addition, there is one student who has the same opinion. According to him, the extroverted personality can be more active in reading activities. His experience is that he likes to read if what he reads is a novel or material that he likes. It can be concluded that there are at least two perspectives in this matter.

Questionnaire

The personality groups of students who were used as research subjects based on the questionnaire were:

Tabel 1

No.	Initial name	Male\female	Personality
1.	AR	Female	introverts

2.	KLB	Male	introverts
3.	R	Female	introverts
4.	KA	Male	extroverts
5.	GA	Female	extroverts

The data above shows that the introverted personality is more dominant. This questionnaire was filled out by representatives of 20 students.

CONCLUSION

Personality is all the traits that can affect a person's situation, especially the way of thinking, feeling and even one's behavior. In the most famous personality is about extrovert and introvert personalities. This study aims to determine whether there is an outcome between personality traits between extroverted and introverted students in reading ability in English reading activities in the second year of Junior high school. Students from MTS Bani Usman Al Buety Based on the results of interviews addressed to several students, most of them answered that their introverted personality played an important role in English reading activities. Introverts prefer to spend time in non-physical activities, such as reading. However, there is one teacher who said that personality does not affect interest in reading or reading activities. Because the teacher said that reading is a mandatory activity that every student must have. In addition, there is one student who has the same opinion.

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